

Stylite Monks

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Stylites were Christian monks who followed in the tradition of the 5th century saint Symeon Stylites the Elder. Symeon, after enduring many years of asceticism on the ground, began living atop high, narrow columns in modern-day Syria. These columns restricted the movement of the saint, so that he could practice an even more rigorous asceticism than he could on the ground, and they allowed the saint to remain more withdrawn from society. Other monks began imitating Symeon almost immediately, and a number of monks still live atop columns today. The highest concentration of stylite monks remained in Syria, but stylites were also present in other regions, such as Cappadocia and Georgia, and numerous stylite saints were recorded in the Byzantine capital, Constantinople. Various saints' lives (hagiographies) attach symbolic meaning to the columns used by stylite saints. Most notably, they may have symbolized the upward movement of monks towards the celestial paradise. Stylites sometimes had a role in affairs on the secular ground, as well, and their spiritual authority was often transferred to social or even political power. For example, Symeon Stylites the Elder once solved a conflict between Theodoret of Cyrus, an important theologian and historian, and the patriarch of Antioch. In Constantinople and the surrounding areas towards the end of the 5th century, the emperor Leo I was a regular visitor of the stylite Daniel, who became, therefore, the spiritual advisor to the political head of state. Later, especially starting in the late 6th century and early 7th century, stylite monks offered their voices to heated debates between Chalcedonian Christians and monophysites, particularly Antiochian stylites, often siding with the latter.

Date Range: 450 CE - 1450 CE

Region: The Eastern Byzantine Empire

Region tags: Asia Minor, Eastern Mediterranean, Levant, Greece, Mediterranean Coast, Eastern Europe, Anatolia, Byzantium

The Eastern Byzantine Empire c. 400 CE.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: R. Doran, "The Lives of Symeon Stylite", Cistercian studies series, Kalamazoo, 1992.
- Source 2: J.-P. Sodini, "Les stylites syriens (Ve-VIe siècles) entre cultes locaux et pèlerinages « internationaux »", Actes des congrès nationaux des sociétés historiques et scientifiques, 2012, 130.14, p. 5-23.
- Source 3: I. Pena, P. Castellana, R. Fernandez, "Les Stylites syriens", Publications du Studium Biblicum Franciscanum, Milan, 1975.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 2 URL: <https://collections.louvre.fr/en/ark:/53355/cl010256428#>

– Source 2 Description: A plaque at the Louvre Museum depicting a stylite saint.

– Source 1 URL: <http://csla.history.ox.ac.uk/record.php?recid=S00343>

– Source 1 Description: Symeon Stylite the Elder in "The Cult of Saints in Late Antiquity" database from the University of Oxford

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <http://csla.history.ox.ac.uk/record.php?recid=E04490>

– Source 1 Description: Evagrius, Ecclesiastical History (1.13-14),

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Other Christians visit Stylite Saints frequently for spiritual guidance. Additionally, they were often in the middle of Theological debates between Chalcedonian Christians and Monophysite Christians.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: For example, the Emperor Leo I makes Daniel the Stylite his spiritual advisor.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Yes

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Stylite monks cannot be grouped into one particular confession of Christianity, but during certain periods of time, a large group of Syrian stylites are openly against the official oecumenical Christian doctrine (Chalcedonian christianity).

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– Yes

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– I don't know

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

↳ Punished in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Cursed by "high god":

– I don't know

↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):

– I don't know

↳ Other divine punishment:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.05

Notes: The number of styllites within the Christian community is low, but their cults can be much larger.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: Each stylite saint may be seen as a leader of his own cult within the larger Christian community.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– Yes

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Stylite monks adhere to the written scriptures of Christianity, notably the Old and New Testaments of the Bible.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: The scriptures are written, but they are also shared orally.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible is a combination of the Old Testament, which is the story of the Jewish people, and the New Testament, which is the story of Jesus Christ, who is said to be the Messiah and the saviour of the world.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: The scriptures are revealed by prophets who are instructed by the one unique

God.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: The New Testament in particular is revealed to be a sort of biography of Jesus Christ, who is one part of the unique tripartite God, so it can be said that the scripture originates from Jesus Christ, who is a divine being.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: The colonnes on which the stylites live are examples of religious architecture, and churches and monasteries are often built around the columns.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 13

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: Churches are often built around stylite columns.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: Altars are present in the churches built around columns, and sometimes altars could be present on top or within the columns themselves, so that stylites could perform the liturgy.

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: The columns and churches could be decorated with devotional markers such as crosses or other Christian symbols.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: The monastery of Qua'lat Si'man, for example, included many places of gathering, and the church itself was conceived to be a place of gathering.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Columns, churches, refectories, pilgrim buildings, baptisteries, etc.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

Notes: Iconographic decoration could be present on columns and in associated churches, and pilgrims could have personal objects with iconography (ampuls, medallions, etc.)

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Yes and no. There is a distinct way to represent stylite monks in iconography (proportionally large monks with pointed hoods on top of proportionally small columns), but the iconography that was present on columns or in the associated churches could be the same as iconography in other Christian buildings.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes a stylized dove can be present above the stylite saint, which symbolizes the Holy Spirit, part of the Unique tripartite God.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: Crosses can be present in depictions of Stylites.

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: The stylites themselves are most often present in the iconography of stylite monks.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: The columns are almost always portrayed in iconographic depictions of stylites, and sometimes ladders are also present.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (rare)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Oriental Christians of the medieval period mostly believe that the soul is separated from the body at death, and that only the soul passes to the afterlife until the second coming of Christ.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: This is true for all oriental christians of the medieval period, but especially for ascetic monks such as stylites, who actively work to suppres the desires and needs of the physical body.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: The bodies of important stylite saints are often venerated.

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– I don't know

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Yes

Notes: Parts of the body may be removed for use as relics.

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– I don't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The Christian God is both anthropomorphic and not anthropomorphic. It is a unique tripartite God (the divine trinity), comprising of the Father, the Son, and the Holy Spirit. The son, Jesus Christ, has both a human and divine nature, and the Holy Spirit can take the form of a dove.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

–Yes [specify]: There is a connection between the Byzantine emperor and God.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

–Yes [specify]: It is a tripartite God comprised of the Father, the Son, and the Holy Spirit (the Holy Trinity)

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: The Christian God is absolutely omnipresent and all-knowing.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

–Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: He is all-knowing.
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The Christian God is often thought to respond positively to prayer.
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
 - Notes: It is thought that the Christian God can punish people with whom he is unhappy. This is especially relevant when studying Symeon Stylites the Younger, who is called upon after a series of natural disasters hit Syria.
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - Yes
 - Notes: God in his Human form possesses hunger (Christ).
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: Several hagiographic sources recount instances of God appearing to people in different forms.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: There are many instances of God appearing to people in dreams.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Ascetic monks, including stylites, spend large periods of time in deep prayer, and sometimes they may enter into what may be described as a trance. These trances are meant to put the monks in closer connection to God, who may or may not appear to them.

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Prayer and intercession. The Eucharist is also considered to be one way people can be in direct communication with God, because it allows them to literally ingest the body of Christ.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Saints are typically not present in physical form, but they are invoked as intercessors after their death.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: There are hagiographic examples of deceased saints who appear to the living and may intervene in the affairs of the living. One famous example is the intervention of Saint Dimetrios at Thessaloniki.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Yes [specify]: They can be invoked as intercessors and can have knowledge, therefore, of the prayers of living beings.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: They are intercessors and therefore intermediaries between God and the living.

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– No

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Saints can be invoked in waking, everyday life as intercessors.
- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Saints can appear to the living in dreams.
- ↳ In trance possession:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Through divination processes:
 - No
- ↳ Only through specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
- ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - Yes [specify]: They communicate with the living mostly through prayer.

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Angels are a main example of non-human supernatural beings that are present.

- ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Stylites may see demons or angels sometimes.

- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - No

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:
– Yes

Notes: The one unique God's incarnated form (Jesus Christ) possessed all human features.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:
– Yes

Notes: The one unique God's incarnated form (Jesus Christ) possessed all human features.

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:

–Yes [specify]: The human-divine being is the one Unique God who is tripartite.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: The one unique God's incarnated form (Jesus Christ) possessed all human features.

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

–Yes [specify]: The human-divine being is the one unique God, and he is Tripartite.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - No
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - Yes [specify]: Prayer

- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes

Notes: There is a hierarchy of different kinds of angels, for example.

- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - No
- ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Yes
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Rape

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: God cares about hygiene in particular contexts.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– I don't know

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– I don't know

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - No
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - No
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
 - No
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
 - No
 - ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– I don't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

- ↳ Other [specify]
- I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
- Yes

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
- I don't know

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
- Yes

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
- Yes

- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
- Yes

- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness[]:
- Yes

- ↳ Done randomly:
- No

- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
- Yes

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Alive, identified:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Coming in this lifetime:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Coming has already passed:
– Yes
Notes: Yes, but there will be a second coming.

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:
– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:
– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:
– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:
– Present and clear
Notes: There are morally superior group of christians, like monks.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

Notes: Courage in battle is emphasized sometimes, but not always.

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - No
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - No

- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - No
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - No
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– No

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– I don't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Celibacy is not required for all Christians, but ascetic monks, including stylites, are expected to abstain from physical desires, including sexual activities.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Stylite monks should abstain from all sexual activity.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Fasting is an important way stylite monks may suppress their physical desires and needs. .

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Stylite monks typically eat a very bland diet. They abstain, for example, from eating meat.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: The ascetic lifestyle of stylite monks typically has a lasting effect on the bodies of the monks.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Yes

Notes: Stylites monks live on top of columns, and often they are not sheltered against the elements. In that way, they put themselves in a position that can be very uncomfortable, or even painful, notably during severe weather.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Stylite monks should sacrifice their possessions when they begin their ascetic lives.

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: For certain people, goods must be abandoned.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: They should spend most of their time in prayer.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: Living atop their columns is a physical risk itself.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: The stylite lifestyle, though it became somewhat political, is, at its base, an isolating and marginalizing lifestyle, requiring stylites.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: In between Eucharistic liturgies, monks participate in the "offices", which are daily organized prayer rituals. They also engage in individual prayer inbetween the offices.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 3

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: They may participate in the Divine Liturgy, though some stylites may not be able to, because of their isolation.

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It depends on the size of the community and the size of the church.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 24

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: There are oecumenical councils that aim to formalize ritual practices, dogma, and theology.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– I don't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: Incense is often used, which may be thought of as intoxicating.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: The Christian church does aim to help the poor and hungry, but not Stylite monks in particular.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The Christian church does aim to help the poor and hungry, but not Stylite monks in particular.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: The Christian church does aim to help the poor and hungry, but not Stylite monks in particular.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: Some stylite monks are part of a larger monastic community, and some of these monastic communities may provide hospice care.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: The stylite monks are part of the Church bureaucracy, but there is no stylite bureaucracy in particular.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: They interact often with Church bureaucracy and state political bureaucracy, notably in their role as spiritual advisors.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: Sometimes the stylite monks are part of a larger monastic complex, which may have irrigation, but it is not always the case.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: Often, monks are exempt from state taxes.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: However, monks are often exempt from state taxes.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: There are special monastic courts, but they are more common in large-scale monastic communities, such as monasteries on Mount Athos.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: Stylites may be part of a monastery where there is institutionalized punishment, but stylites themselves do not typically enforce punishment.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: A stylite may be part of a monastery with a formal code, but it is not a necessity for a stylite.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They are subject to the formal legal code of the state.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They may be protected by the Byzantine army, for example.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the languages associated with stylite monks are Greek, Syriac, and Georgian.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the languages associated with stylite monks are Greek, Syriac, and Georgian.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: They follow the Christian liturgical calendar.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They follow the Christian liturgical calendar.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Patoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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